

D2.4 Third short report of cluster events

Author: Alexandre Torres Ferreira

Contributor: Stefanie Schuerz

30.09.2025

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the European Citizen Science (ECS) project Consortium under EC grant agreement No. 101058509 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

All European Citizen Science (ECS) Consortium members are committed to publish accurate and up to date information and take the greatest care to do so. However, the consortium members cannot accept liability for any direct, indirect, special, consequential or other losses or damages of any kind arising out of the use of this information.

Acknowledgment

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Reference

Please cite this work as:

Torres Ferreira, A., Schuerz, S. (2025) D2.4 Third short report of cluster events. ECS project. (first version).

Copyright Notice

This work by Parties of the European Citizen Science (ECS) Consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence.

Document Identification Sheet

Project Ref. No.	101058509
Project acronym	ECS
Project Full Name	European Citizen Science
Document Name	ECS_D2.4_Third short report of cluster events_v1.0
Dissemination Level	PU
Contractual Date of Delivery	31.07.2025
Actual Date of Delivery	30.09.2025
Type	R – Document, report
Deliverable number	D2.4
Deliverable name	Third short report of cluster events
WP / Task / Lead Beneficiary	WP2 / T2.5/ SD
Number of pages	32
Authors	Alexandre Torres Ferreira (SD)
Contributors	Stefanie Schuerz (ZSI)
Reviewers	Jorge Barba Borderías (IBE), Stefanie Schuerz (ZSI), Carolina Doran (ECSA)
Project Officer	Irina Elena Tiron
Abstract	This deliverable provides a short report with key takeaways from the 2025 cluster event "Advancing Public Engagement and Citizen Science in the European Research Area" and its satellite event, the "Citizen Science Fair". The event served as a strategic platform to showcase EU-funded projects and formulate co-created policy recommendations for embedding citizen science and public engagement in the FP10 framework.
Keywords	ECS, citizen science, public engagement, science communication, ORRI, cluster event, policy recommendations, European Research Area, FP10, stakeholder engagement

Table of contents

Version Log	5
List of definitions and acronyms	6
Executive Summary	7
1. Cluster event rationale	8
1.1. Context	8
1.2. Objectives	8
1.3 Event overview	9
Satellite event: Citizen Science Fair	9
Main event: Advancing Public Engagement and Citizen Science in the ERA	10
2. Key takeaways on advancing public engagement and citizen science in the ERA	10
Takeaway #1: A unified cross-community voice enables strategic policy integration	10
Takeaway #2: The community-driven Position Paper demonstrates citizen science strategic maturity and implementation readiness	11
Takeaway #3: Sustainable funding mechanisms are essential for long-term community development	12
Takeaway #4: Project impact storytelling demonstrates tangible value to policymakers	12
Takeaway #5: Community-driven infrastructure development is a strategic priority	13
Takeaway #6: Public engagement demonstrates broad societal appeal and accessibility	14
3. Event evaluation	14
Main event evaluation	14
Citizen Science Fair Evaluation	15
4. Conclusion and next steps	15
4.1. Immediate Outcomes	15
4.2. Strategic Next Steps	15
References	17
Annex I. Detailed agenda of the ECS cluster Event 2025	18
Annex II. Satellite event list of participants	20
Annex III. Cluster event survey results	23

Version Log

Version	Date	Released by	Nature of Change
0.1	03.09.2025	Alexandre Torres Ferreira (SD)	First draft
0.2	08.09.2025	Jorge Barba Borderías (IBE)	First review
0.3	17.09.2025	Alexandre Torres Ferreira (SD)	Second draft
0.4	19.09.2025	Stefanie Schuerz (ZSI)	Second review, added annex on evaluation of the cluster event
0.5	28.09.2025	Alexandre Torres Ferreira (SD)	Third draft, added chapter on evaluation of the cluster event
0.6	29.09.2025	Carolina Doran (ECSA)	Third review
1.0	29.09.2025	Alexandre Torres (SD)	Final version ready for delivery

List of definitions and acronyms

Acronym	Expansion
CS	Citizen science
EC	European Commission
ECS	European Citizen Science
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
REA	Research Executive Agency
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
R&I	Research and Innovation
FP10	10th Framework Programme for Research and Innovation
PE	Public engagement
ORRI	Open Responsible Research and Innovation
RIECS	Research Infrastructure for Excellent Citizen Science
CSGP	Citizen Science Global Partnership

Executive Summary

As one of its core goals, the European-funded project ECS - European Citizen Science aims to strengthen and broaden the citizen science community across Europe.

The present D2.4 Short report of the 2025 cluster event highlights the key insights gathered from the 2025 cluster event, which took place in Brussels on June 19th, 2025, preceded by a satellite "Citizen Science Fair" on June 18th. The main event, titled "Advancing Public Engagement and Citizen Science in the European Research Area," brought together 80 in-person participants including citizen science practitioners, project coordinators, policymakers from the European Commission, and national representatives, plus an additional peak online viewership of 81 unique individuals. Participants and online viewers represented a wide range of countries and institutional backgrounds.

The event focused on strategic positioning for the 10th Framework Programme (FP10) and demonstrated both the maturity of the public engagement field in contributing to European Research Area priorities, as well as the impact that citizen science and public engagement initiatives have generated with the funding provided by the European Commission.

A core achievement of this event was the policy roundtable discussion featuring joint policy recommendations compiled by four major EU projects - ECS, REINFORCING, COALESCE, and IMPETUS - representing a unified cross-community voice from the citizen science, science communication, and open responsible research and innovation fields. This discussion addressed recommendations across several critical dimensions and demonstrated how public engagement and citizen science must be positioned as both a horizontal enabler across all FP10 clusters and missions, and a vertical objective with dedicated funding streams.

Another pivotal moment of the event was the fishbowl session "ECSA and the future of citizen science in Europe: Platform, Infrastructure and Vision," which prominently focused on the [Position Paper](#) co-created by the European citizen science community and coordinated by ECS and the [ECSA Working Group on Policy, Strategy, Governance and Partnerships](#), and showcased the strategic alignment between several different initiatives within the citizen science community, such as the proposed pan-European Research Infrastructure for Excellent Citizen Science (RIECS), the mature ECS Platform and Academy infrastructures, and global collaboration through the Citizen Science Global Partnership (CSGP). This session demonstrated the community's readiness to move from fragmented initiatives toward systematic, infrastructure-supported integration of citizen science in European research policy.

Both the main and satellite events showcased a remarkable combined number of 50 citizen science and public engagement projects across both days, including 19 projects featured in dedicated impact pitch sessions demonstrating concrete research, policy, societal, and institutional outcomes, alongside 28 initiatives presented at the public Citizen Science Fair. This comprehensive project representation demonstrated the diversity and maturity of the European citizen science ecosystem.

Key takeaways of the events include the need for systematic embedding of public engagement in FP10, sustainable funding mechanisms, strengthened community infrastructures exemplified by the ECS Platform evolution and RIECS conceptualisation, and enhanced policy integration pathways supported by global networks like CSGP. The satellite Citizen Science Fair, taking place a day earlier at the Garden of the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, successfully engaged the broader public, providing hands-on experiences and setting an inclusive tone for the policy discussion.

1. Cluster event rationale

1.1. Context

The European Commission's commitment to public engagement (PE) and citizen science (CS) as central pillars of Open Science has fostered a broad ecosystem of EU-funded projects (alongside national and regional initiatives) over the past decade. These initiatives have generated vast impact through substantial evidence, methodologies, and policy insights, demonstrating the value of participatory approaches in enhancing research quality, societal relevance, and public trust in science.

The timing of the 2025 cluster event was strategically chosen to coincide with critical discussions about the 10th Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (FP10), which will define Europe's R&I landscape from 2028 to 2034. This presents an unprecedented opportunity to move beyond fragmented, project-based initiatives toward systematic, infrastructure-supported integration of public engagement approaches into the structural framework of the European Research Area (ERA).

This strategic imperative is reinforced by recent high-level policy reports. The Draghi Report (European Commission: European Political Strategy Centre, 2025) emphasises the need to transform Europe's innovation model to ensure technologies serve broad societal interests and reflect public values. The Letta Report (Letta, 2024) warns that growing perceptions of innovation disparities risk eroding public support for European integration, particularly among citizens in lagging regions who fear being left behind by technological transformations. Most significantly, the Heitor Report (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2024) explicitly proposes the establishment of a "Societal Challenges Council" to engage civil society in shaping R&I priorities, perfectly aligning with the need to institutionalise structured dialogue between citizens, policymakers, scientists, and industry.

As articulated in the policy recommendations developed over the years by the public engagement community, including those within the [Position Paper](#) (ECSA Working Group on Policy, Strategies and Partnerships, ECS project, & wider European Citizen Science community, 2025) developed collaboratively by the European citizen science community, citizen science, participatory science communication, and Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) are increasingly recognised as essential mechanisms to democratise innovation, legitimise complex transitions, enhance research quality, and bridge territorial and socio-economic divides.

Against this backdrop, the 2025 Cluster Event was designed to facilitate dialogue among policy, community and infrastructure actors by bringing together representatives from diverse project communities. The event drew participation from major coordination initiatives besides ECS, such as REINFORCING, COALESCE, and IMPETUS, alongside specialized thematic projects including COESO, CROPS, DITOs, EU ALBATROSS, INCREASE, MICS, ScienceUs, WeCount, ACTION, AURORA, CrAFt, CoAct, COS4Cloud, Critical Making, FRANCIS, HuMUS, and YouCount/YouHope. This convergence of projects allowed for cross-project learning and the identification of shared challenges and opportunities to inform discussions about future directions for public engagement in European research policy.

1.2. Objectives

The 2025 ECS Cluster Event and its satellite fair were guided by the following key objectives:

Showcase the value of citizen science and public engagement: Demonstrate to policymakers the significant impact and societal relevance of public engagement and citizen science as tools for evidence-based policy-making through the comprehensive representation of 50 projects across both events. Highlight the role of public engagement and citizen science in supporting the [ERA Policy Agenda](#), namely Action 14, through fostering inclusion, reinforcing trust in science, bringing the public closer to research, and addressing societal challenges through scalable and collaborative approaches that maximize resource efficiency.

Highlight best practices: Present successful public engagement strategies and innovative approaches implemented in Horizon2020 and Horizon Europe projects through dedicated impact pitch sessions featuring 19 initiatives, demonstrating concrete outcomes across R&I, policy, societal, and institutional domains to inspire and guide further initiatives.

Contribute to guiding future policy: Develop and present actionable recommendations for integrating public engagement and citizen science into future EU Work and Framework Programmes, particularly FP10, through both cross-community coordination (joint recommendations from four flagship projects) and community-driven strategic vision ([Position Paper "Citizen science for the future of Europe"](#)), showcasing their potential to enhance research, innovation, and societal impact while aligning with the ERA Policy Agenda's focus on "Citizen Engagement, including trust in science for a stronger and more democratic European society."

Celebrate important achievements: Host the 2025 EU Citizen Science Prize winner announcement, reinforcing the importance of public engagement in science and recognizing outstanding contributions to the field while fostering community pride and motivation.

Community building and knowledge sharing: Foster collaboration among the diverse ecosystem of EU-funded R&I projects with a strong focus on Public Engagement, covering topics such as citizen science, open science, open and responsible research and innovation, science communication, co-creation and co-design. Strengthen networks across the 22 projects represented at the main event and provide accessible public engagement through the 28 initiatives featured at the Citizen Science Fair.

Demonstrate public appeal and accessibility: Through the satellite Citizen Science Fair, provide direct hands-on engagement opportunities for the broader public, demonstrating the inclusive and accessible nature of citizen science while setting a welcoming tone for the policy-focused discussions and reinforcing the democratic values underlying public engagement in research.

The event targeted a diverse audience including EU policymakers, project coordinators from Horizon Europe and national initiatives, academic researchers, civil society representatives, and practitioners from across the public engagement spectrum.

1.3 Event overview

Satellite event: Citizen Science Fair

- **Date:** June 18, 2025 (10:30-17:00)
- **Organisers:** ECS, Scivil, Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
- **Location:** Garden of the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences

- **Format:** Free public event with interactive exhibitions and live demonstrations
- **Participation:** 28 citizen science initiatives from Belgium and across Europe
- **Activities:** Hands-on data collection experiences, networking opportunities, project showcases

Main event: Advancing Public Engagement and Citizen Science in the ERA

- **Date:** June 19, 2025 (9:00-18:30)
- **Organisers:** ECS, IMPETUS, REA
- **Location:** REA, Brussels (hybrid format with streaming)
- **Attendance:** 80 in-person participants, 81 peak online viewers
- **Key Sessions:**
 - Opening keynote and policy context setting
 - Policy roundtable with presentation of joint recommendations from Horizon Europe projects ECS, COALESCE, REINFORCING, and IMPETUS
 - Impact pitches from 19 citizen science and public engagement projects
 - Fishbowl session on strategic vision and infrastructure development for citizen science in Europe
 - EU Citizen Science Prize 2025 winner announcement
 - Networking lunch with poster presentations

2. Key takeaways on advancing public engagement and citizen science in the ERA

The 2025 cluster event provided a strategic platform for high-level discussion on embedding public engagement systematically within European R&I policy. Drawing from the policy roundtable, project pitching sessions, fishbowl discussions, and networking activities, **six key takeaways** emerged that reflect the community's maturity and readiness to contribute meaningfully to the future European Research Area.

Takeaway #1: A unified cross-community voice enables strategic policy integration

The policy roundtable featured joint policy recommendations compiled and presented by representatives from four flagship EU projects - ECS, REINFORCING, COALESCE, and IMPETUS - representing citizen science, science communication, and open responsible research and innovation (ORRI) communities. Facilitated by Marzia Mazzonetto (Stickydot), this session demonstrated significant cross-community coordination, showing how different public engagement domains share common strategic needs and can present unified policy solutions around comprehensive policy dimensions:

Institutional and structural strengthening, emphasising the need for professionalisation through formal career paths, dedicated roles within research institutions, and integration of public engagement competencies into academic promotion criteria. The recommendations specifically call for modernising reward and recognition

systems, implementing CoARA principles (Arentoft et al., 2022), and embedding public engagement into formal research frameworks.

Sustainable funding mechanisms, moving beyond traditional project-based approaches towards innovative models including cascading grants for engagement with stakeholders that are typically underrepresented in citizen science (such as SMEs, local governments, farmers, artists), micro-grants with simplified procedures, and dedicated funding streams that support cross-sector collaboration and long-term infrastructure sustainability.

Participation and inclusion, addressing the critical need for evidence-informed, participatory approaches that enable meaningful engagement of communities marginalized from scientific research, often due to geographic, economic, or cultural barriers, and who are critical to engaging for achieving equitable and relevant outcomes. The recommendations call for funding instruments designed for inclusion, with extended timelines for trust-building and simplified application procedures.

Impact maximisation, focusing on consolidating pathways between citizen-generated data and policy decision-making, thereby grounding EU missions in local context and enabling tangible citizen contributions to global challenges. This involves strengthening integration into EU monitoring systems, and fostering dialogue between local implementation teams and policy-setting institutions to address disconnect between community-level activities and policy outcomes.

Training and capacity building, outlining the need for comprehensive infrastructure supporting future-proof skills development, aligned with EU competency frameworks, and specifically calling for the development of science communication competence frameworks.

Data integration and embedment, emphasising the need to establish common standards, create interoperable platforms, and ensure compatibility with existing research infrastructures while strengthening policy integration to increase public trust in science.

These discussions showed that for public engagement to contribute strategically to EU priorities such as competitiveness, innovation, and societal resilience, it must be positioned as both a horizontal enabler across all FP10 clusters and missions, and a vertical objective with dedicated funding streams. Framing public engagement in this dual role is key in reinforcing ERA and FP10 objectives such as advancing the Green Deal, enabling the digital transition, and fostering inclusive societal resilience.

Takeaway #2: The community-driven Position Paper demonstrates citizen science strategic maturity and implementation readiness

The fishbowl session prominently featured the community-driven Position Paper “Citizen science for the future of Europe”, showcasing the strategic maturity and implementation readiness of the European citizen science community. Co-created by the European citizen science community and jointly coordinated by the ECSA Working Group on Policy, Strategy, Governance and Partnerships and the ECS Consortium, this comprehensive document represents a strong community mobilisation around a unified strategic vision.

The position paper articulates 5 key recommendations, calling for (1) a dedicated citizen science programme line in FP10, building on H2020’s “Science with and for Society” success; (2) mainstreaming citizen science principles across all FP10 funding calls; (3) sustainable funding through mechanisms including multi-year grants and upscaling effort; (4) grassroots funding through accessible micro-grants and simplified procedures; and (5) open topic calls enabling citizen-driven, bottom-up research addressing societal challenges.

Through the fishbowl session, it was demonstrated how this community-driven strategic vision aligns with concrete infrastructural developments including the ECS [Platform](#) and [Academy](#) (mature community resources), the proposed conceptualisation of the [Research Infrastructure for Citizen Science \(RIECS\)](#), and global collaboration through the Citizen Science Global Partnership (CSGP). This alignment between strategic vision, existing infrastructure, and international partnerships positions the citizen science community as implementation-ready for systematic FP10 integration and thus ERA equipped to contribute to EU policies like the Green Deal.

Takeaway #3: Sustainable funding mechanisms are essential for long-term community development

Across all sessions, participants highlighted the limitation of having only short-term, project-based funding for citizen science and public engagement initiatives. Such funding, while important, was considered insufficient on its own for building lasting engagement infrastructures and communities, leading instead to a fragmented landscape. The discussions revealed several innovative funding approaches needed for FP10:

Infrastructure sustainability: Funding streams for digital platforms that have evolved from project outputs to community-essential resources, alongside sustained investment in proposed pan-European research infrastructure for enhanced data interoperability and cross-sector collaboration.

Inclusive participation funding: Recognition that engaging underrepresented groups, such as marginalized communities, SMEs, and rural participants, who contribute essential knowledge and context, requires dedicated and tailored resource models. As highlighted by IMPETUS project representatives, this includes micro-grants with simplified procedures, extended timeline allowances for trust-building, and cascading grant mechanisms to reach community-based organisations.

Institutional change support: Dedicated funding within FP10 to support the professionalisation of public engagement, including training programmes, capacity building, and the implementation of modern reward and recognition systems aligned with CoARA principles (Arentoft et al., 2022).

These funding models not only address the sustainability of citizen science but also align with ERA and FP10 priorities to foster inclusiveness, strengthen research infrastructures, and support Europe's green and digital transitions.

Takeaway #4: Project impact storytelling demonstrates tangible value to policymakers

The two project pitching sessions, thematically organised around R&I/Policy impacts and Societal/Institutional impacts, proved highly effective in demonstrating the concrete value of public engagement approaches. The highly limited format (5 minutes, maximum 3 slides, focus on specific impact types) allowed presenters to showcase the breadth of value propositions provided by citizen science and public engagement projects.

The 19 projects that delivered pitch presentations were: COALESCE, COESO, CROPS, DITOs, EU ALBATROSS, INCREASE, MICS, ScienceUs, WeCount, Contribution of citizen science to SDG monitoring, ACTION, AURORA, CrAFt, CoAct, COS4Cloud, Critical Making, FRANCIS, HuMUS, and YouCount/YouHope. Key shared messages emerged from the presentations:

- **Policy integration success stories:** Projects demonstrating how citizen-generated data successfully informed local, national, and EU-level decision-making processes.
- **Research quality enhancement:** Examples of how public participation improved research design, data quality, and solution relevance.
- **Community empowerment outcomes:** Concrete instances where engagement activities led to improved living conditions, enhanced local capacity, and strengthened social cohesion.
- **Institutional transformation:** Cases where projects catalysed changes in academic reward systems, research practices, and institutional engagement policies.

The synergy between the project pitches and policy roundtable demonstrated that the community has moved beyond anecdotal impact stories toward systematic evidence that supports comprehensive policy integration. The pitches provided the empirical foundation for the policy recommendations, while the joint recommendations provided the strategic framework for scaling successful project approaches across FP10. This complementarity between impact pitches and policy recommendations showed a maturity of practice that positions citizen science as a ready partner in FP10 implementation.

Takeaway #5: Community-driven infrastructure development is a strategic priority

The fishbowl session, "Taking stock and looking forward" provided crucial insights into the community's infrastructure needs and aspirations. Facilitated by Carolina Doran (ECSA), the session brought together key representatives from the community and beyond to discuss the strategic alignment of current and future infrastructural developments with European research priorities.

The ECSA Position Paper, co-created with the European citizen science community and represented by Franziska Stressmann from ECSA, outlines five key recommendations and ten supporting recommendations for embedding citizen science at the heart of the European Research Area (ERA). This forward-looking vision articulates a clear strategy for the continued growth, professionalisation, and institutional integration of citizen science across Europe. The position paper serves as both a strategic guide and a call to action for researchers, institutions, funders, and policymakers to work collaboratively in making citizen science a fundamental part of Europe's scientific and democratic fabric.

The ECS Platform and Academy, represented by Dorte Riemenschneider from ECSA, demonstrates the maturity of community-driven digital infrastructure. Built by the community, for the community, these tools have evolved from project outputs to essential community resources supporting knowledge exchange, capacity building, and professional development. The platform serves as a central hub for practitioners to share resources and find collaborators, while the Academy provides curated training materials and learning pathways that empower effective citizen science engagement across sectors.

The RIECS concept project, presented by Fermin Serrano from Ibercivis, has strong community endorsement as a necessary next step for scaling citizen science impact. This proposed pan-European research infrastructure will address critical needs for data interoperability, quality assurance frameworks, sustainable funding models, and enhanced cross-sector collaboration. The co-creation approach being adopted ensures community ownership and fit-for-purpose design, with inclusive activities involving practitioners, policymakers, researchers, citizens, and other end-users.

The Citizen Science Global Partnership (CSGP), represented by Dilek Fraisl from IIASA, highlights the importance of international collaboration and knowledge sharing in strengthening the European citizen science ecosystem. CSGP's global perspective provides valuable context for European initiatives and facilitates the

exchange of best practices across continents, ensuring that European developments contribute to and benefit from worldwide citizen science advancement.

The European Commission representative provided closing remarks on how the Commission will move forward based on the fishbowl discussion, indicating strong institutional interest in the infrastructure developments and strategic vision presented.

This session demonstrated the strategic alignment between ECSA's vision, existing community infrastructures, proposed research infrastructure, and global collaboration networks, positioning the citizen science community as implementation-ready for systematic integration into European research policy frameworks.

Takeaway #6: Public engagement demonstrates broad societal appeal and accessibility

The satellite Citizen Science Fair, held on June 18th in the Garden of the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, successfully achieved its objective of demonstrating the accessibility and appeal of citizen science to the broader public. With 28 citizen science initiatives from across Belgium and Europe, which are listed in Annex II, this free, open-access event featured:

Interactive demonstrations from diverse citizen science initiatives, allowing visitors to experience firsthand the roles and contributions of citizen scientists. The hands-on activities effectively demystified scientific participation and showcased the diversity of engagement opportunities.

Networking and knowledge exchange between established practitioners and potential new participants, fostering the expansion of the citizen science community. The informal setting encouraged dialogue between scientists, policymakers, and citizens in a relaxed, welcoming environment.

Public celebration of (citizen) science that reinforced the inclusive and democratic values underlying the public engagement movement. The event's success in attracting diverse audiences, from families to students to policy practitioners, demonstrated the broad appeal of participatory science approaches.

The fair also served to contextualise the subsequent policy discussions, reminding all participants of the ultimate beneficiaries and collaborators in their work: engaged citizens across Europe and lending legitimacy to the policy dialogue. By showcasing inclusiveness and accessibility, the fair also reinforced FP10 priorities on citizen participation, societal resilience, and the democratisation of knowledge.

3. Event evaluation

Post-event evaluation surveys were conducted for both the main cluster event and the satellite Citizen Science Fair to assess participant satisfaction, learning outcomes, and strategic impacts. The evaluation results provide valuable insights into the event's effectiveness and areas for future improvement (detailed results are provided in Annex III).

Main event evaluation

43 participants responded to the survey, representing both in-person (23) and online (20) attendees. The participant profile reflected the event's target audience with 60.5% identifying as academics/researchers,

20.9% as public engagement professionals, and 11.6% as policymakers. Notably, 90.7% of respondents had previous citizen science experience, indicating strong community engagement.

Session ratings were consistently positive, with project pitches receiving the strongest feedback (23 "excellent" ratings), followed by the fishbowl discussion (21 "excellent" ratings) and policy roundtable (17 "excellent" ratings). Participants strongly agreed that the event was interesting (33 of 43), succeeded in demonstrating concrete impacts (37 agreed), and provided valuable networking opportunities (31 agreed).

Regarding impact conviction, participants expressed strongest belief in citizen science effectiveness for policy impact (32 "very convinced"), followed by social impact (32 "very convinced") and scientific impact (30 "very convinced"). Economic and technological impacts received more mixed responses, suggesting areas where community messaging could be strengthened.

Citizen Science Fair Evaluation

The public fair received overwhelmingly positive feedback through simplified smiley-scale evaluations in three languages. Responses to questions about liking the event, learning about citizen science, future participation intentions, and belief in citizen science's potential to improve the world were consistently positive, with minimal negative responses.

4. Conclusion and next steps

The 2025 ECS Cluster Event brought together stakeholders to discuss public engagement and citizen science in the context of European R&I policy, featuring presentations of policy recommendations, strategic planning documents, and impact demonstrations from 19 projects across different domains. The event mobilized representatives from 50 initiatives across the two-day programme, providing an opportunity to highlight the scope and depth of impact generated by citizen science and public engagement initiatives, as well as a broad perspective on current work in the European public engagement field. The policy roundtable's presentation of joint policy recommendations, developed collaboratively across four major projects, combined with the strategic alignment demonstrated in the fishbowl session between ECSA's vision, existing infrastructures, and future developments, represents a crucial step toward systematic integration of participatory approaches in European R&I policy.

The strategic timing of the event, coinciding with FP10 preparation discussions, positions the recommendations to directly influence the next framework programme's design. The demonstrated community readiness, evidenced through mature infrastructures like the ECS Platform, collaborative policy development processes, and concrete impact examples, provides a strong foundation for the proposed systematic integration.

4.1. Immediate Outcomes

- Finalisation of the cross-community joint policy recommendations and presentation to the European Commission, representing the unified voice of the citizen science and public engagement community
- Strengthening of community ties through enhanced networking, resource sharing, and collaborative relationships established during the event
- Expansion of the evidence base through the documentation of project impacts and best practices shared during the pitching sessions
- Demonstration of public engagement through the successful Citizen Science Fair, providing concrete evidence of broad societal appeal

4.2. Strategic Next Steps

The insights and recommendations from the event will directly inform several key activities:

FP10 advocacy and input: The joint recommendations serve as the foundation for ECSA and partner organisations' contributions to FP10 consultation processes, pushing for public engagement perspectives to be systematically integrated into the framework programme design.

Infrastructure development: The strong support expressed for RIECS-concept development will guide the next steps in conceptualising and proposing this pan-European research infrastructure, with community input mechanisms established with the support of the ECS Platform.

Community sustainability: The ECS project will continue fostering the strengthened community through its Collaboration Group bi-monthly meetings, ensuring momentum from the event is maintained and collaborative relationships continue to develop.

Institutional integration: The evidence of impact and institutional benefits documented at the event will support ongoing efforts to embed citizen science and public engagement in academic reward systems, funding criteria, and institutional strategies across member states.

Policy monitoring and engagement: The established relationships with EC representatives and policy stakeholders will enable continued dialogue and input as FP10 implementation approaches, ensuring community perspectives inform operational decisions.

The 2025 cluster event represented not just a reporting milestone for the ECS project, but a strategic opportunity for the public engagement community to present coordinated policy recommendations through the policy roundtable, showcase strategic planning through the fishbowl session, and demonstrate concrete impacts through project pitch presentations. The event notably mobilized representatives from 50 projects across the two-day programme, providing a comprehensive view of the European public engagement ecosystem.

References

Arentoft, M., Berghmans, S., Borrell-Damian, L., Bottaro, S., Faure, J-E., Gaillard, V., Glinos, K., Albacete, J. L., Morais, R., Morris, J., Schiltz, M., & Stroobants, K. (2022). Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13480728>

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. (2022). European Research Area policy agenda : overview of actions for the period 2022-2024. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/52110>.

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. (2024). Align, act, accelerate : research, technology and innovation to boost European competitiveness. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/9106236>.

European Commission: European Political Strategy Centre. (2025). The future of European competitiveness. Part A, A competitiveness strategy for Europe. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2872/9356120>.

ECSA Working Group on Policy, Strategies and Partnerships & the European Citizen Science project & the wider European Citizen Science community of practice, Albert, A., Doran, C., Gold, M., Haklay, M., Heinisch, B., Kieslinger, B., Oesterheld, M., Riemenschneider, D., Serrano Sanz, F., Schuerz, S., & Stressmann, F. (2025). Citizen science for the future of Europe (full version). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1505676>

Letta, E. (2024). Much More Than a Market-Speed, Security, Solidarity: Empowering the Single Market to deliver a sustainable future and prosperity for all EU Citizens. <https://coilink.org/20.500.12592/vmcvm07>

Annex I. Detailed agenda of the ECS cluster Event 2025

Location: REA, Boulevard Simon Bolivar 34, 1000 Brussels, Belgium Auditorium, 13th floor

Time (CEST)	Content
8.30 - 9.00	Welcome & registration
9.00 - 9.10	Introduction <i>Marc TACHELET, REA Director</i>
9.10 - 9.20	Short icebreaker <i>Marzia Mazzonetto, Stickydot</i>
9.20 - 9.50	Keynote Speech: Public Engagement in the ERA (web-streamed) <i>Jean-David MALO, Acting Director 'European Research Area & Innovation', European Commission, DG Research and Innovation</i>
9.50 - 10.50	Roundtable Policy Recommendations for Future Frameworks (web-streamed) <i>Moderated by Marzia MAZZONETTO (Stickydot)</i> <i>Speakers: Carolina DORAN (ECS), Angela SIMONE (REINFORCING), Joana MAGALHAES (COALESCE), Alexandra ALBERT (IMPETUS) and Georgios PAPANAGNOU, (DG Research and Innovation)</i>
10.50 - 11.10	Coffee break
11.10 - 12.15	Project pitches #1: R&I and Policy Impact <i>Moderated by Alexandre TORRES FERREIRA (Stickydot)</i> <i>Speakers: Joana MAGALHAES (COALESCE); Alessia SMANIOTTO (COESO); Catarina PYDZINSKA AZEVEDO (CROPS); Muki HAKLAY (DITOs); François GREY (EU ALBATROSS); Roberto PAPA (INCREASE); James SPRINKS (MICS); Rafaella LENOIR IMPROTA (ScienceUs); Kris VANHERLE (WeCount); Dilek FRAISL (Contribution of citizen science to SDG monitoring)</i>
12.15 - 13.30	Networking lunch & project showcase
13.30 - 13.40	Recap from Citizen Science Fair <i>Annelies DUERINCKX, Scivil</i>
13.40 - 14:30	Project pitches #2: Societal and Institutional Impact <i>Moderated by Dorte RIEMENSCHNEIDER</i> <i>Speakers: Gefion THUERMER (ACTION); Ana BELÉN CRISTOBAL LOPEZ (AURORA); Annemie WYCKMANS (CrAFt); Josep PERELLÓ (CoAct); Jame PIERA (COS4Cloud); Stefanie</i>

	<i>SCHÜRZ (Critical Making); Liza WOLFAHRT (FRANCIS); Annalaura VANNUCCINI (HuMUS); Aina LANDSVERK HAGEN (YouCount/YouHope)</i>
14.30 - 15:15	Fishbowl session: Taking stock and looking forward (web streamed) <i>Moderated by Carolina DORAN (European Citizen Science Association)</i>
15.15 - 15.45	Coffee break
15.45 - 16.45	Winners Announcement: EU Citizen Science Prize 2025 (web streamed) <i>Co-hosted by Marc TACHELET (REA Director), Minna WILKKI (Head of Department; REA.C), Gefion THUERMER (IMPETUS), Vanessa HANNESCHLÄGER (IMPETUS)</i>
16.45 - 17.00	Wrap-Up & Closing Remarks <i>Minna WILKKI, Head of Department, REA.C</i>
17.00 - 18.00	Reception

Annex II. Satellite event list of participants

Project	Explanation	EN/NL/FR
1. Scivil - Citizen Science Flanders	Scivil connects and supports citizen science projects through collaboration and innovation.	EN/NL
2. Amai! - Deel je idee voor AI	Get to know AI solutions for everyday problems.	EN/NL
3. Telraam	Telraam is a traffic-counting device for citizen-led data collection.	EN/FR/NL
4. Mijn Tuinlab	An interactive platform for citizen science projects in gardens.	EN/NL
5. ECSA	The European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) was set up to encourage the growth of citizen science in Europe, and to support the participation of the general public in research processes	EN/FR
6. From Bystander to Hero: Towards a Heartsafe North-West Europe	In the heart of North-West Europe, the Heartsafe NWE project represents a powerful and forward-thinking endeavor. Fueled by strategic collaboration and innovative solutions, its core mission is to substantially enhance survival rates.	EN/NL
7. Plastic Pirates Belgium	Plastic Pirates Belgium supports schools and youth groups to research the plastic pollution in a river or coastal area in their neighbourhood.	EN/NL
8. Grote Schelpenteldag	This initiative teaches us a lot about the distribution of these marine creatures, the impact of climate change, and the presence of exotic species. By joining hundreds of nature enthusiasts, you help researchers gain a better understanding of our sea.	EN/NL
9. The MOMENT of spatial justice	Women's safety in Brussels varies by time, place, and context.	EN/NL
10. Urban ReLeaf	Innovating together for just and green urban transitions.	EN/FR/NL
11. VUB Citizen Science Contactpunt	Supporting all things citizen science at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel.	EN/NL
12. Strengthening mental health and resilience through schools	This project aims to co-design a sports-based mental health programme in Brussels schools.	EN/NL

13. City Confessions	Educational board game empowering bystanders to address street harassment.	EN/FR/NL
14. Lichens GO	Lichens GO is a citizen science programme that aims to assess air quality in your local area by studying the different species of lichens growing on trees.	EN/FR
15. HARISSA: Natural HAZards, RISks and Society in Africa	Will you survive the next disaster? Discover how citizen science boosts natural hazard knowledge and community resilience.	EN/FR
16. ATRAP: Action Towards Reducing Aquatic snail-borne Parasitic diseases	sNailed it: Unlocking the potential of citizen science to control snail-borne diseases.	EN/FR/NL
17. SurveillanceMoustiques/ MuggenSurveillance & TiquesNet/TekenNet	Citizens can help out monitoring the tiger mosquito in Belgium by taking a picture of the mosquito and report it on the platform. Citizens can help out monitoring ticks by reporting tick bites.	EN/FR/NL
18. De Grote Voedselkaart	Map your food environment: your input shapes healthier communities!	EN/FR/NL
19. BUGS: Benefits of Urban Green Spaces	Investigating the health benefits of urban parks and their microorganisms.	EN/NL
20. The Isala sisterhood	Global effort to improve women's health.	EN/FR
21. Isala and its daughter projects: let's swab!	Investigating vaginal microorganisms and its influencing factors on women's health.	EN/NL
22. Ferme Scholen	Harnessing vegetable fermentations to increase microbial literacy in the classroom.	EN/NL
23. De Oorzaak	The largest citizen science project regarding environmental noise in Flanders.	EN/NL
24. Bodemdierendagen	Discover the secret yet invaluable Tiny Ten in your garden!	EN/NL
25. VIB Grand Challenge: Soy 2.0	Validating the use of endemic rhizobia for sustainable soybean cultivation in NW Europe.	EN/NL
26. COMPAIR: Together for better air!	Take a walk with us and discover local air quality.	EN/NL

27. VOSS

Citizen volunteers tackle marine litter through beach cleanups and monitoring.

EN/FR/NL

28. The DASA website

DASA opens up bat sounds collected by citizen scientists.

EN/FR/NL

Annex III. Cluster event survey results

Cluster Event: Advancing Public Engagement and Citizen Science in the ERA

Update 28.07.2025

Survey results

43 people responded to the survey, of which 27 (62,8%) identified as female, 29 (67,4%) were aged between 36-55, and only 4 (9,3%) had no previous experience with citizen science. 26 participants (60.5%) identified as academics/researchers, 9 (20,9%) as public engagement professionals, and 5 (11,6%) as policymakers or people working in public institutions.

Gender identification
43 responses

Age group
43 responses

Did you have any previous experience with citizen science?

43 responses

Which of the following profiles do you most closely identify with? (Check all that apply)

43 responses

Of the respondents, 23 participated on site and 20 online.

The **pre-event organization** and **interactivity of the event** were seen as overwhelmingly positive or neutral, with only one “poor” rating for the pre-event organization.

Looking at the sessions themselves, the **project pitches** received the strongest positive feedback, with 23 participants rating the session as “excellent” and 12 as “good”. Second- best rated was the **fishbowl discussion** with 21 “excellent” and 15 “good” ratings, but also receiving the only “very poor” rating. The **policy roundtable** received 17 “excellent” and 17 “good” ratings, as well as one “poor” rating. Finally, the **European Citizen Science Prize**

winners' announcement received 19 "excellent" and 12 "good" ratings, with the highest numbers of participants of 7 indicating the category of "prefer not to say", which does not distinguish between opinions and people who did not participate in the respective sessions.

How would you rate the following aspects of the event?

Looking at the statement-ratings, 33 of 43 respondents indicated they strongly agreed that the event was interesting to them, with 7 indicating agreement, and 1 indicating disagreement. 31 people found the event to be a good networking opportunity (with one person strongly disagreeing), and 37 strongly agreed or agreed that the event succeeded in demonstrating the concrete impacts of European citizen science and public engagement projects (with 2 people disagreeing and 1 strongly disagreeing). 38 found the event an occasion to learn something new (with 1 person disagreeing and 1 strongly disagreeing), while 35 found the event succeeded in highlighting different policy priorities for citizen science and public engagement (with 3 people disagreeing and 1 strongly disagreeing).

Please read the following statements and tell us to what extent you agree or disagree with each of them.

In terms of concrete impacts, the survey asked participants to indicate for each impact area

how convinced they are that citizen science (CS) and public engagement (PE) are effective ways to achieve change. Here, **social impact** received the strongest responses with 31 respondents indicating they were “very convinced” and 9 indicating they were “convinced”. This was followed by **scientific impact**, with 30 “very convinced” and 6 “convinced” respondents, but also 3 “unconvinced” respondents. **Policy impact** had 32 “very convinced” and 16 “convinced” respondents, and **institutional impact** had 22 “very convinced” and 13 “convinced” respondents, with both impact areas having 2 “unconvinced” respondents each. For **ecological impact**, 25 respondents were “very convinced” that CS and PE were effective ways to achieve change, and 13 were “convinced”. The least clear belief in the effectivity of CS and PE was shown for **economic impact**, with 15 “very convinced” and 14 “convinced”, and for **technological impact**, with 16 “very convinced” and “convinced” respondents each. Both impact areas had 3 “unconvinced” respondents.

The event aimed to showcase the kinds of impact citizen science and public engagement may achieve. Following the event, please tell us for each impact area how convinced you are that citizen science and public engagement are effective ways to achieve change:

The **most important takeaways** included statements indicating that citizen science was mature, that PE and CS must be a key element of the next EU R&I policies, and that the event helped to gain an understanding of the directions and implementation plans for citizen science in different countries. Other statements outlined how the event was a good opportunity to gain knowledge, to get to know wonderful projects and learn more about CS, and to gain awareness of the CS approach and the importance of CS in all areas. The opportunity for networking was also much appreciated, while the enthusiasm and commitment of the CS community was underlined, as was the inspiring work so many different projects are doing and the motivation it brought to bring together lots of people working on the same kinds of things

The event also showed that CS is growing, that the network is solid and that there are a lot of efforts in advancing CS on a European level, but also that we need more art and culture in

science; that there is a lot of agreement in the community about what we need to make citizen science succeed, and the policy goals to support that; and the need for continued efforts to mainstream CS that is aligned with policy priorities, but that there was a need to strengthen this idea to wider policy audiences.

Participants also found that there is a lot going on in the EU, and that it is worth listening to the experiences of others – the projects, the frameworks, all the valuable information. That it was important to continue supporting the PE-CS-Scicomm-OS communities in order to foster stronger connections and their consolidation for an effective and real action on science with and for society. There was also a need expressed for more opportunities to connect as communities with the REA, and an appreciation to understand to what extent they cared about CS. Being listened to by senior REA stakeholders and other decision makers attending the event, and feeling heard, was also stressed as an important takeaway.

On a technical level, someone pointed out that the online transmission was perfect, they felt like they were on site – which was true also for the recording. One respondent also mentioned that their most important takeaway – besides the impact of citizen science initiatives on different topics – was the existence of the EU-citizen.science platform.

One single respondent voiced how they did not find the event worth repeating. Another one stated that *“As long as EU supports AI and neglects real human experiences, we will not have a citizen science valorizing people's experiences of problems, emotions, civic imagination.”*

On the question on **additional recommendations to drive policy that supports citizen science and public engagement**, statements included a need for a central repository that registers and consolidates all CS initiatives and provide links to individual websites; greater recognition of CS as a valid research methodology, coupled with dedicated funding streams, to help integrate PE more systematically into the scientific process; the need to support small organisations and actors also from the EU level, and to address the complexity and bureaucracy of existing EU funding instruments that currently exclude smaller organisations; to provide specific additional budgets in all Horizon projects for CS activities developed by expert CS partners; a drive for more community empowerment that will themselves change perhaps their ground environment and less of a focus on having a direct policy impact; and a focus on more long-lasting outcomes and evaluations. One statement mentioned the need to encourage

academic credit and career recognition for researchers who engage citizens

One respondent noted that they hoped to see more comprehensive commentary, including some insights on teams that were not selected as winners for the EU Citizen Science Prize. Another respondents would have liked to have a moderated peer-learning process among projects instead of panels. Others asked for more events like this; to invite both citizens and policymakers to events like this, and co-create results based on CS approaches and methods; and to engage more with national and subnational policy makers. One respondent stressed that CS is not a technology, and that we need new ways of experimenting and co-creating knowledge well beyond the divide policymaker/policytaker. Finally, one respondent singled out the fishbowl session as the one they loved.

The **further comments** opened up two important points of critique / reflection: First, that there was a lot of room for improvement in differentiating outputs/outcomes/impacts. And second, that the awarding of the prizes did not take place unannounced, as the winners were already connected online or present at the event. This aspect really surprised one respondent, who indirectly realized that they had no chance of winning. This indicated a bit of a mismatched expectation management that might be addressed should the EU Citizen Science Prize be continued beyond IMPETUS:

Aside from these two statements, further comments entailed only the following messages:

- Thank you for the event, it was great!
- Excellent organisation
- Thanks for hosting a great event!
- thank you so much
- Congratulations from Ecuador!!! I learnt a lot.
- Thank you and congratulation for the organisation of this important and fruitful meeting!
- Thank you for the opportunity! :-)
- Thank you for organising a wonderful event!

Feedback on the Citizen Science Fair

As part of the Citizen Science Fair 2025, held one day before the Cluster Event at the Garden of the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences in Brussels, leaving guests were asked to provide

feedback by means of an event evaluation post. Since the event was aimed at a broad audience, the poster contained five easily understandable questions in three languages (English, French and Dutch) which asked for feedback with a smiley-scale indicating strong disagreement to strong agreement:

1. I liked the event
2. I learned something about citizen science
3. I want to participate in citizen science activities in the future
4. I want to tell others about citizen science after this event
5. I think citizen science can help make the world a better place

Responses to these questions were overwhelmingly positive. One negative response was given to questions 2 (“I learned something about citizen science”) and 3 (“I want to participate in citizen science activities in the future”) respectively, while questions 3 and 4 (“I want to tell others about citizen science after this event”) received 4 and 6 mid-range responses respectively.

While the feedback posters were positioned on the central tent and the entrance gates, not all participants left feedback. The stickers to provide feedback were hung up with the posters to allow for a certain amount of privacy to respondents while they gave feedback.

ecs

European
Citizen
Science

ecs
Scivil
Citizen Science
Vlaanderen
natural
sciences
.be

Citizen Science Fair 2025

A Celebration of Citizen Science

rate your experience

I liked the event - J'ai aimé l'événement - Ik vond het evenement leuk

I learned something about citizen science - J'ai appris quelque chose sur la science citoyenne - Ik heb iets geleerd over citizen science

I want to participate in citizen science activities in the future - Je souhaite participer à des activités de sciences citoyennes à l'avenir - Ik wil in de toekomst deelnemen aan citizen science-activiteiten

I want to tell others about citizen science after this event - Après cet événement, je veux parler à d'autres personnes de la science citoyenne - Na dit evenement wil ik anderen vertellen over citizen science

I think citizen science can help make the world a better place - Je pense que la science citoyenne peut contribuer à rendre le monde meilleur - Ik denk dat citizen science de wereld kan helpen verbeteren

eucitsciproject

eu-citizen.science

Funded by the
European Union

